

1 **Mitochondrial vulnerabilities in the circulating tumor cell.**

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6 The circulating tumor cell is the biologic identity that manifests a multi-organ system disease from the
7 primary tumor. We measured total transcription in the circulating tumor in humans with two separate types
8 of solid tumor disease for identification of a CTC gene signature and therapeutic vulnerability including
9 targets on the mitochondria. We identified mitochondrial genes *MICU3* and *IMMP2L* as therapeutic targets
10 in the circulating tumor cell. In both humans with prostate cancer and in humans with breast cancer,
11 *MIPEP* was a mitochondrial vulnerability in the solid tumor CTC. Systems biologic study suggested the
12 mitochondrial genes functioned in branched chain amino acid catabolic processes involving the genes
13 *BCKDHB* and *HIBADH*.
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